

A-M Variable & Attribute Table Instructions

Morris and Akish (2022)

Sara Morris (sara.morris@noaa.gov), Elena Akish (elena.akish@noaa.gov)

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The table is intended for Merged Observatory Data Files (MODF) makers to use in developing their merged data files. As an MODF maker is gathering metadata about their observations, they can put all of the metadata for each of their variables into this spreadsheet. The spreadsheet has four tabs for the Global Attributes of the MODF, for the timeSeries Variables, for the timeSeriesProfile Variables, and for the trajectoryProfile Variables. Once populated, this spreadsheet can be read into any MODF toolkit developer software as a means of reading in the metadata for the MODF variables.

The descriptions for the attributes within the table can be found in the documentation of The H-K Variable Schema Table developed for the YOPPsiteMIP (Hartten & Khalsa, 2022), and are also listed at the end of this document. These attributes are considered mandatory (if applicable).

Attribute Descriptions

actual_range - The smallest and the largest valid non-missing values occurring in the variable

comment - Miscellaneous information about the data or methods used to produce it

contributor_email - Email of Responsible Party

contributor_name - Responsible Party

conventions - List of the conventions that are followed by the dataset

creator_email - Email of the person responsible for creating this data

creator_name - The name of the person responsible for creating this data

date_created - The date on which this version of the data was created (not considering changes to metadata)

featureType - One of the following, as of 15 Sept 2021: 'point', 'timeSeries', 'trajectory', 'profile', 'timeSeriesProfile', or 'trajectoryProfile' (see http://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-conventions/cf-conventions-1.9/cf-conventions/html#_features_and_feature_types)

history - Provides an audit trail for modifications to the original data

id - Persistent Identifier (PID) for dataset

institution - Institution where the original data was produced

instrument - Type of instrument used to collect measurement

keywords - Comma-separated list of key words and/or phrases, preferably drawn from a controlled vocabulary, e.g. the GCMD at <https://earthdata.nasa.gov/earth-observation-data/find-data/gcmd/gcmd-keywords>

license - Terms of distribution and use

long_name - A descriptive name that indicates a variable's content; identified in the H-K Table variable descriptions

metadata_link - URL to detailed documentation (DOIs expressed as [http://doi.org/...](http://doi.org/))

missing_value - A value or values used to represent missing or undefined data. Allowed for auxiliary coordinate variables but not allowed for coordinate variables

naming_authority - Naming authority for PID (preferably using reverse-DNS naming, e.g. 'edu.ucar.unidata', although URIs may be used)

original_name - Name of the original variable in the original file from which it came

project - Name of the project(s) principally responsible for originating this data

references - Published or web-based references that describe the data or methods used to produce it

short_name - Shortened name that indicates a variable's content; identified in the H-K Table variable descriptions

source - The method of production of the original data. If it was model-generated, name the model and its version. If it is observational, characterize it.

standard_name - A standard name that references a description of a variable's content in the standard name table

standard_name_vocabulary - Name and version of the controlled vocabulary from which variable standard names are taken

summary - A paragraph describing the dataset

time_coverage_end - The time of the last data point in the data set

time_coverage_start - The time of the first data point in the data set

title - Short human-readable phrase or sentence describing the dataset

units - Units of the variable; requested MODF units identified in H-K Table variable descriptions

References and Links for Attribute Definitions:

- 1) Hartten, Leslie M., & Khalsa, Siri Jodha S. (2022). The H-K Variable SchemaTable developed for the YOPPsiteMIP (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6463464>
- 2) Eaton, B. et al. (2021). NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Conventions (1.9). <http://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-conventions/cf-conventions-1.9/cf-conventions.html#attribute-appendix>